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TEORETYCZNE RAMY DLA ROZWOJU PRZYWÓDZTWA PRZYSZŁYCH MASTERS

Oleksyiy Koryakin

doktor nauk pedagogicznych,

Sumy State Pedagogical University nazwany na cześć A.S. Makarenko, (Sumy, Ukraina)

prof_extreme@mail.ru

Adnotacja. Artykuł poświęcony jest teoretycznym zasadom rozwoju konstruktywnego przywództwa przyszłych mistrzów profilu humanitarnego w procesie kształcenia zawodowego. Artykuł przedstawia stan rozwoju problemu rozwoju konstruktywnego przywództwa przyszłych mistrzów profilu humanitarnego, a także istotę konstruktywnego przywództwa. Użyliśmy następujące metody: analiza literatury filozoficznej, pedagogicznej i psychologicznej studiować zjawisko przywództwa i analizy systemowej strukturalny badać zawartość i strukturę konstruktywnego przywództwa. Zastosowano również ogólne metody naukowe: analizę, syntezę, indukcję i dedukcję. Artykuł podkreśla również główne koncepcje przywództwa: koncepcje, które uzasadniają przewagę cech osobowości; koncepcje, w których decydującym czynnikiem jest sytuacja; koncepcje łączące czynniki osobiste i sytuacyjne. W badaniu określono pojęcie „konstruktywnego przywództwa” i proponowanej definicji „dominacji lidera” w dyskursie zawodowego przyszłych mistrzów Humanistycznych.

Słowa kluczowe: konstruktywne przywództwo, dominacja przywództwo przywództwo funkcjonalne dysfunkcyjnych przywódcze, neutralny przywódcze, przyszli mistrzowie humanistycznych pojęcie czynniki osobiste, sytuacyjne pojęcie, pojęcie kombinacji czynników sytuacyjnych i osobistych.

THEORETICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF LEADERSHIP OF THE FUTURE MASTERS

Oleksyiy Koryakin

candidate of pedagogical sciences,

Sumy state pedagogical University named after A.S. Makarenko, (Sumy, Ukraine)

Abstract. The article is devoted to theoretical principles of development of constructive leadership of future masters of the humanitarian profile in the process of professional training. The article describes the state of development of the problem of development of constructive leadership of the future masters of the humanitarian profile, as well as the essence of constructive leadership. The following methods were used: the analysis of philosophical, pedagogical and psychological literature in order to study the phenomenon of leadership, as well as system-structural analysis in order to study the content and structure of constructive leadership. Also were used general scientific methods: analysis, synthesis, induction and deduction. The article also outlines the main concepts of leadership: the concepts that justify the advantage of the factor personality traits; concepts in which the decisive factor is the situation; concepts that combine personal factors and situational. As a result of the study, the content of the concept of «constructive leadership» is specified and the definition of «leadership domination» in the discourse of professional training of future masters of the humanitarian profile is proposed.

Key words: constructive leadership, leadership domination, functional leadership, dysfunctional leadership, neutral leadership, future masters of the humanitarian profile, personal conceptions, situational conceptions, conceptions of the combination of situational and personality traits.

ТЕОРЕТИЧНІ ЗАСАДИ РОЗВИТКУ ЛІДЕРСТВА МАЙБУТНІХ МАГІСТРІВ

Олексій Корякін

кандидат педагогічних наук,

*Сумський державний педагогічний університет імені А.С.Макаренка,
(Суми, Україна)*

Анотація. Стаття присвячена теоретичним засадам розвитку конструктивного лідерства майбутніх магістрів гуманітарного профілю в процесі професійної підготовки. В статті окреслено стан розвитку проблеми розвитку конструктивного лідерства майбутніх магістрів гуманітарного профілю, а також сутність конструктивного лідерства. Використовувались такі методи: аналіз філософської, педагогічної та психологічної літератури з метою вивчення феномену лідерства, а також системно-структурний аналіз для вивчення змісту та структури конструктивного лідерства. Також були використані загальнонаукові методи: аналіз, синтез, індукція та дедукція. У статті також висвітлено основні концепції лідерства: концепції, що обґрунтовують перевагу фактору рис особистості; концепції, в яких вирішальним фактором є ситуація; концепції, які поєднують особистісні та ситуаційні фактори. В результаті дослідження конкретизується зміст поняття «конструктивне керівництво» та запропоновано визначення «лідерського панування» в дискурсі професійної підготовки майбутніх магістрів гуманітарного профілю.

Ключові слова: конструктивне лідерство, лідерське домінування, функціональне лідерство, дисфункціональне лідерство, нейтральне лідерство, майбутні магістри гуманітарного профілю, концепції особистісних факторів, ситуаційні концепції, концепції поєднання ситуаційних та особистісних факторів.

Introduction. The content of the phenomenon of leadership and approaches to its development attracted the attention of researchers of various fields throughout the development of human civilization. B. Bass and R. Bass indicate that the study of the essence of leaders and leadership began simultaneously with the emergence of civilization, and also emphasize the fact that in leadership, military and social movements, leadership plays an important, if not the most important, role, respectively, it is an important subject of research (Bass & Bass, 2009). Problems of leadership development in higher education institutions are L. Kaidalova, O. Kin (students in general), N. Marahovsky, K. Kiba, O. Krupsky, N. Semenchenko, T. Ivanova, G. Titov (future teachers), A. Pilganchuk, (future psychologists), B. Goloshko, O. Romanovsky (future managers), L. Sergeev, V. Kondratiev, M. Khromey (future specialists in the specialty «Commercial affair»), S. Kalashnikov (future leaders of educational institutions) and others. The problems of the personality of the leader are devoted to the scientific works of such researchers: B. Bass, R. Bass (Bass & Bass, 2009), K. Blanchard, P. Bons, H. Downey (Downey, Sheridan & Slocum, 1976), F. Fiedler, S. Green, P. Hersey, J. Homans, B. Lloyd (Lloyd, 1996), M. Mumford, R. Vecchio and others. However, the aspect of the theoretical foundations for the development of constructive leadership of future masters of the humanitarian profile in the process of vocational training is not sufficiently covered in the research papers. Therefore, the purpose of the paper is to deepen the differentiation of the typology of leadership, to specify the definition of «constructive leadership» and to define the concept of «leadership domination» in the discourse of the process of training future masters of the humanitarian profile.

Main part.

Objectives of the research: differentiation of the basic concepts of leadership, specification of types of leadership depending on the direction of influence on the goals of the group, clarification of the definition of «constructive leadership» and the definition of «leadership domination» in the discourse of the process of training future masters of the humanitarian profile. The results of the research on the development of constructive leadership of the future masters of the humanitarian profile in the process of professional training are set out in the dissertation for obtaining a scientific degree of the candidate of pedagogical sciences (Ph.D.) and discussed at scientific and practical conferences of different levels, the list of which is set out in the abstract of dissertation for obtaining a scientific degree of the candidate of pedagogical sciences.

The term «leader» comes from the verb «to lead», consequently, «leads» and «leads oneself». This is an indicator of autonomy and activity. Problems of leadership are studied in management, pedagogy, psychology, sociology, political science and biology. The problem of leadership is presented in the scientific literature quite broadly, but yet there is no single general theory of leadership. The overwhelming part of scientific research is devoted to the general aspects of the personality of the leader. The variety of theories dealing with leadership are usually reduced to consideration of why one or another person becomes a leader.

In modern social sciences, there are four main theoretical approaches that explain the leadership abilities of a person and the phenomenon of leadership in the group. This is a biographical approach to leadership, «the theory of personal rice», situational, and synthetic leadership theory.

The main content of the biographical approach is that leadership potential is determined not only by the specific features and characteristics of the individual, but also by all previous experience. Proponents of the biographical approach argue that true leaders go to the top of their career throughout their lives, and leadership is always a logical end, culminating in previous experience.

According to the theory of rice and its varieties that arose under the influence of the research of the English psychologist and anthropologist F. Galton, who tried at the beginning of the twentieth century to explain leadership on the basis of heredity (within this direction were carried out studies of the royal dynasties of different nations, the analysis of marriages between rulers etc.), the leader possesses the qualities inherited, which distinguishes him from his followers, and these qualities can be distinguished. Only in 1940, the psychologist C. Bird compiled a list of 79 rice, called various researchers as «leader» (Bird, 1940). Not so successful attempts to distinguish this kind, doubts about the possibility of this led to the life of the concept of constellation of rice (constellation - any well-organized matrix). The success of leadership is determined by the extent to which the individual features the leader. The presence of the appropriate features makes a person a leader in all conditions. If the constellation of the features is complete, one can speak of a prominent leader.

In accordance with the situational theory of leadership (or, as it is called G. Gibsh and M. Forverg, «group dynamic approach»), the emergence of a leader is the result of place, time and circumstances, while the theory of rice in this conceptual scheme is not completely excluded. The situational leadership theory emphasizes the relative character of the features inherent to the leader, and suggests that qualitatively different circumstances may require qualitatively different leaders. Considering the motivation

and need of the personality of leader G. Gibsh and M. Forverg distinguish as the leading motive of topical leadership activity, the motive of power, potential leadership activities - self-realization.

In most modern, most popular theoretical approaches, leadership is no longer identified with a separate function or a set of conventionally separated mental processes, as was common in a number of theoretical models of the past. In our time, leadership is not limited to a «set of personal characteristics» or «dependence on the situation».

The synthetic theory of leadership combines the practical significance of the situational theory of leadership and the «stability» of the theory of personality traits. The most striking representatives are G. Homans (Homans, 1974), F. Fiedler (Fiedler, 1964). This theory is an attempt to create an extra-rational model of leadership, in particular F. Fiedler offers his variant – «probabilistic model of leadership effectiveness», which focuses on integrating the influence of the leader (or rather, his personality traits) and situational variables (relations between the leader and followers, the essence task, degree of leadership power). The adherents of this theory argue that only the combination of a certain set of personality traits with a situation favorable to the carrier of these traits, can create an effective leader.

In addition to the above, one can consider other theories of leadership, which have become less widespread. In the «humanistic» theories, it is argued that the human being by its nature is a complex motivated organism, and the organization is, in principle, always guided. Therefore, the leader must transform the organization so that the individual is provided with freedom to realize his personal goals, needs, and at the same time, in order to contribute to the goals of the organization.

Representatives of existential psychology associate the ignorance of leadership positions with the search for both the content of being and themselves, emphasizing that only in interaction with other people can find themselves. The need for self-realization prevails in adolescence, a person at this stage of development seeks to realize his potential; in this connection, there is an urgent need to learn about his own abilities; for this, not only self-evaluation is required, but also an assessment from the group, only in this case, an individual can form an adequate self-assessment of his own capabilities. Considering the leader as the key link of interaction, they claim the primacy of leadership nature («art») in relation to technology as a set of methods and techniques of leadership of the group («science»). Researchers point out the need for special training for leaders of small groups.

In terms of behaviorism, leadership is available to any member of the group, with some of them successful in one form of activity, others - in another. Within the limits of psychology, which adheres to the positions of behaviorism, distinguish the following sources of leadership: the quality of personality, allowing her to take leadership positions, the quality of followers that promote the separation of the leader; the structure of the group that consolidates the leadership status. The qualities that make it possible to take leadership positions, both congenital and formed, and gain reinforcements in the process of communication and joint activity.

Proponents of the biological theory point to a special quality, which should be inherent in the leaders and given to them from birth - this is dominant. In the very concept of «domination» laid biological meaning; this advantage is by force, the size of maximum physical quantities. But a dominant person does not always put forward a leadership position in the human community, and may often be marginalized.

Domination is the direct opposite of leadership, which carries socio-psychological content, free of violence and generated as a result of group interaction: the leader leads, not depresses, his power - in the mind and ability to lead oneself. Today, one domination is not enough to be a leader; necessary special psychological qualities, abilities, skills, knowledge of psychology of people, theory and practice of communication. Even the leader's giftedness, whose existence is noted by biographers of prominent figures, can only be found in the relevant social conditions.

According to S. Green, reality cannot be understood solely from the standpoint of biological determinism (Green & Liden, 1980). Biological formations - heredity, domination, and desire for power - are not a guarantee of ignorance of leadership positions and can be considered as one of some but not the only factors that influence the formation of a leader. Leadership activity can not develop outside the society, outside the group, a person in the process of communication knows the leadership roles and functions, leadership experience. In this approach, along with the external reality, with its requirements, it is necessary to take into account also the reality of the internal, subjective, due to the existence of the inner world of the individual.

Summarizing, it is possible to note, that in modern scientific literature, in addition to the above, there is a large number of diverse leadership concepts that can be divided into three groups:

A. Concepts that justify the advantage of the factor personality traits (K. Blanshard, P. Hersey, R. Diltes, F. Ilyasov, E. Hollander, J. Julian and others).

B. Concepts in which the decisive factor is the situation (P. Johnson, T. Mitchell, J. Larson (Mitchell, Larson & Green, 1977), F. Fiedler (Fiedler, 1964) and others).

C. Concepts, which combine personal factors and situational (S. Bagretsov, G. Homans (Homans, 1974), K. Ohanyan, F. Fiedler and others).

The analysis of the domestic and foreign concepts leads to an understanding that leadership is not only the relationship of domination and subjugation, influence and follow-up in the system of interpersonal relations in group, but this is what happens inside the subject in terms of his own life and activities; this process is not only interpersonal, but also internally personal.

The research is based on an integrated concept of the combination of personal and situational factors of constructive leadership that embraces both the leadership's own aspirations and the specific situation in which it can be realized. In accordance with these concepts, the phenomenon of leadership is represented depending on the direction of influence on the realization of the goals of the group: as a constructive (functional), contributing to the goals of the group; as destructive (dysfunctional), which is formed on the basis of aspirations that harm the group; as neutral, which does not directly affect the performance of the group.

The goals of constructive leadership are to create «movements» in the broadest sense of the word (for example, the movement for civil rights, publicity etc), progressive measures and reforms, the development of the world, the elimination of injustice, etc. Obviously, metallurgy is typical for people with an intense perception of the surrounding world, a sense of personal responsibility for everything that happens in society.

The second kind is macro-leadership. His goal is to create a successful organization, organizational culture and finding a way to a successful future. The next kind of leadership is micro-leadership, aimed at creating an effective working

atmosphere and encouraging colleagues to strive for co-operation in the execution process

It is advisable to add another component to this classification - leadership for yourself. His goal for a leader is to realize himself, to succeed, to be recognized by others. Thus, the purpose of leadership directs the person to self-knowledge and understanding of others. However, the leader self-actualizes «for himself» at the expense of his own achievements, and a person inclined to domination is realized at the expense of other members of the group.

The effectiveness of leadership is determined differently in models of foreign researchers. Thus, in the scientific works of F. Fiedler - this is the level of performance of the task by the group under the leadership influence (Fiedler, 1964). In the scientific works of B. Bass, K. Blanchard, and P. Hersey the satisfaction of the followers is added even further, when the change in behavior under the influence of leadership brings to man satisfaction (Hersey & Blanchard, 1960).

The following approaches to the interpretation of leadership can be defined:

A. Leadership is a kind of power, the specifics of which are the direction from the top down, as well as the fact that its carrier is not the majority, but one person or group of persons.

B. Leadership is the managerial status, the social position associated with decision making, this leadership position. Such an interpretation of leadership stems from the structural-functional approach, which implies consideration of society as a complex, hierarchically organized system of social positions and roles. Classes in this system are positions associated with the implementation of managerial functions (roles), and gives a person the status of a leader.

C. Leadership is the influence on other people, which is mainly positive.

Consequently, the leader is called the personality, according to which all other members of the group recognize the right to assume the most responsible decisions that affect their interests, and determine the direction and nature of the activities of the entire group. In our research, the term «leader» is defined as a person - a future master of humanities who, in the process of his training, implements leadership in the process of interaction with other future masters.

It is important to note that the nomination of a constructive leader is a small group, so it is advisable to study the mechanisms of nomination of leaders in a small group, selected on the basis of the analysis of psychological and pedagogical scientific works.

A. «Natural selection», on the principle «wins the strongest». The given mechanism was used in the era of primitive relations, in the literal sense, but still operates today in conditions of market competition: in the figurative sense, the strongest - the most frugal, the most decisive. Such a mechanism can be favorable for nominating a constructive leader, but it is not always effective for a steady leader position in a group, because, in addition to perseverance, it should have other characteristics for solving group tasks.

B. Formal, based on heredity, high origin, status or position, without taking into account the individual leadership characteristics of a person. This tradition is typical of our time, when the leader's nomination is due to family, family, friendly, ideological, party connections. This gradually leads to the rebirth of leadership in leadership, the leader himself - the leader, and his environment - in the «clan» (narrow, closed group

associated with the circular commitment of people). Persons put forward by such a person, there is a need to constantly maintain a stable structure of the group by cultivating the belief in its infallibility. The perception of reality of such a person becomes irrational, because the relationship between him and his environment loses a reasonable basis, for example, the leader perceives everything new, alien and hostile. This mechanism is more peculiar to the nomination of a person prone to leadership domination, and not constructive leadership.

C. «Valuable exchange». Personality is promoted to the position of a constructive leader due to the potential that is valuable to the group. Of all the variety, the features of the leader are evaluated primarily by those who directly contribute to the strengthening of the team. The personality of the leader identifies the system of group norms and values, therefore his nomination is conditioned by the effectiveness of his contribution to solving the group task. In this regard, business or personal characteristics of the leader may prevail. Such a mechanism for the nomination of a leader is characteristic of highly organized groups, is effective, since it is carried out in an honest manner and gives the leader the opportunity to show himself in group activities.

D. «Emotional attraction». This mechanism of nomination of constructive leaders is inherent in poorly organized groups, which show visible, but insignificant personality traits for a true team (increased verbal and physical activity, liveliness, perseverance, etc.). As a result, there is an installation on the surface reflection of the individual, leading to a shortage of information about people and the complication of organizational interaction, especially in stressful situations. On the same basis there is a tendency to exaggerate the role of certain individuals in the life of the team from the side of emotionally close to them people.

It deserves attention to the analysis of the ways of constructive leadership, the practical experience of which contributes to the development of constructive leadership of future masters of the humanitarian profile. They provide a coherent interrelated work of the leader and subordinates (followers) to solve group tasks. Researchers emphasized that the choice of one or another method depends on the type of power of the leader - the power, which is based on the formal position and personal qualities, the authority of the leader. Among methods based on formal power, the following are distinguished:

A. Orders, orders, coercion - the division between subordinate tasks that are subject to strict implementation.

B. Informing - messages and explanations of the essence, the values of certain principles, norms and rules of conduct, ways of achieving the goal, necessary for the performance of work.

C. Remuneration - payment, promotion, appointment, but rewards are not necessarily material: it may be a proposal status, approval, recognition, admission to a group of elected;

D. Punishment - criticism, refusal to support or friendship, lowering the position, reducing earnings, dismissal, temporary removal from office, cancellation of bonus payments, etc., and there may be enough conviction in the existence of punishment

Among methods based on power of leader's authority the following are distinguished:

A. Appeal to feelings, needs - the leader's support for essentially important things for subordinates in order to awaken and develop the necessary feelings in them and positive attitude towards the fulfillment of tasks, achievement of the goal;

B. Involvement in new active activities - the leader provides the subordinates with the opportunity to receive interesting work and training in order to develop their skills, to strengthen their faith;

C. Suggestion - the influence on the behavior of a person imperceptibly to her, penetration into the mental structure of the individual and realization in everyday life in deeds, aspirations, motives and attitudes; belief - influence on consciousness, the will of subordinates, which contributes to the formation of their new views, attitudes or changes to previous ones,

D. Example - influence on consciousness, feeling, behavior of subordinates through the imitation of the leader, identification with himself, acceptance of his attitudes and values. A leader can encourage subordinates to social identification - identifying themselves with a group or organization, feeling that membership in them is one of the most important aspects of life;

E. Competition - the induction of subordinates to finding the best ways to solve problems, development of activity, creative possibilities on the basis of comparison of results;

F. Advice - the influence on the subordinates, based on the recognized mastery of the leader in a particular field, but his advice will only be considered until his skill is recognized and accepted;

G. Empowerment - giving Subordinates greater freedom in decision-making, opportunities to realize hidden talents, demonstrate resourcefulness and creativity to achieve group goals.

Researchers indicate that the methods based on the authority of the leader's authority have a pronounced motivating effect on the subordinates, so that the latter will work more efficiently and will be satisfied with the leader. This paradox is explained by the fact that the methods of formal power are necessary for the daily management of a group and subordinates under customary circumstances. However, authorities based on authoritative methods are most effective in addressing issues that go beyond the routine management, as well as issues that require subordinates of devotion to the group and the person who manages it.

Developing the views of the researchers, we believe that the leader needs to know: himself (their weak and strong sides); followers (peculiarities of their character, motives, interests, etc.); group (group aspirations, values, norms, traditions, etc.); own activity (ways of its implementation). It is important that the leader was able to: regulate his own emotional state, use different ways of self-regulation, manage himself, appearance; create a clear picture of the future state, which is both optimistic and achievable, and transfer its values to followers; understand people, their relationships, see hidden conflicts, solve them; stimulate followers, encourage, transform the goal into action through raising expectations, reducing the complexity of problem solving to key issues, personal example; manage the working self-feeling of the group in the process of performing tasks; 6) set goals, assign tasks, delegate authority, monitor group activities, monitor and evaluate results; 7) use non-traditional methods and techniques of work.

Scientists offer different characteristics of leaders, mechanisms for their nomination and the influence of the leader on the group and conclude that leaders with advanced moral qualities, able to perform socially useful functions and support socially meaningful relationships in the group are characterized as constructive leaders.

However, pedagogical practice notes that individuals who have other personal qualities do not always constructively affect the group and, based on their functions, generate a phenomenon of domination. Such people are characterized as individuals inclined to dominate the leadership, characterized by a desire for power, an overestimation of self-esteem, a desire to govern, ignoring the opinions of others. By rejecting the biological interpretation, dominance is mentioned in the work of the Brazilian teacher P. Freire in «Pedagogy of the oppressed», in which he, analyzing the disadvantages of traditional forms of learning, points to the oppression of the students and the dominance of the teacher over them (Freire, 2000). Domination is understood as supremacy, the desire to dominate, to rule, to exercise its power without having sufficient grounds to satisfy, first of all, its own aspirations and interests.

Leadership domination, in contrast to leadership, is characterized by the following features: active life position in relation to one's own life; realization of life plans at the expense of own potential and opportunities of group members; characterized by a high appreciation of herself as an active figure in her own life; the desire to dominate, to receive recognition, need positive reactions from others, from simple confirmation of basic abilities; the desire of the authorities; self-knowledge as a basis for realizing its own potential and exercising its power; the desire to avoid failures and the need for achievements; the desire to be in the group, playing the role of a leader, not being really like that; perceives itself capable, if necessary or in a favorable coincidence of circumstances, to lead others, pursuing primarily their own goals.

Some attempts to separate dominance into a separate psychological phenomenon (if rejecting a purely biological interpretation) can be found in the writings of R. Vecchio and M. Mumford (Vecchio & Gobdel 1984), (Mumford, 1986) but they relate to a greater understanding of the organizational aspect and treat domination as a form of management of subordinates or from a political point of view. However, in the discourse on the training of future masters of the humanitarian profile, the definition of «domination» was not considered.

The complexity and ambiguity of the phenomena of leadership domination and constructive leadership requires the development and use of appropriate diagnostic tools. Leadership dominance as a socio-psychological phenomenon covers a wide range of issues and areas of educational and social life of future artists. Impact is caused not only with the purpose and in the interests of the group directly related to the process of training. This phenomenon also manifests itself in the cases of the life and activities of people who are indirectly associated with the educational process. That is, leadership domination and constructive leadership in the educational process are very significant. They can be considered as an attribute of a group that has its own structure and function. This process unfolds in the context of the professional training of future masters and depends on the success of the formation of the group.

The structure of leadership domination in the group is formed in spatial-temporal characteristics, reflecting, first of all, the level of development of the academic group of future masters of the humanitarian profile. At the same time, a stable system of relations, connected with the unequal status of future masters and their contribution to joint activity, can reveal not only the formed interpersonal relations, but also the level of their moral and psychological dependence, in other words, psychological power.

High degree of compliance of individuals with the norms of constructive leadership, updating them relevant leading type of joint activity of the type of personal

orientation, interpersonal compatibility with members of the academic group - all this serves as a peculiar value contribution to individual members of the social group, exemplified by the academic group of future masters of the humanitarian profile and, ultimately, the group as a whole; with contributions that really affect the decision of the tasks facing the group in different spheres of its activities and, accordingly, provide those members of the group who made a certain contribution the corresponding status in the main blocks (dimensions) of the group leadership system.

Constructive leadership and leadership domination were determined by us through interrelated characteristics. In particular, the characteristics of «leadership domination» are acquired by future masters of the humanitarian profile with the following indicators: leadership qualities in terms of dominance, high level of desire for power, personal orientation to power, high level of anxiety, high self-esteem, low emotional attractiveness, average communicative distance and are characterized by low assessment by others and self-esteem in the leadership scale. Characteristics of «constructive leadership» are acquired by future masters of the humanities, with leadership qualities in terms of dominance, low or average level of aspiration to power, personal orientation to power, low level of anxiety, adequate self-esteem, high emotional attractiveness, small communicative distance and are characterized by a high score. on the other hand, and self-esteem on the leadership scale.

A common phenomenon of leadership domination and constructive leadership can be considered that these phenomena are developing in a small group, implemented in the process of educational activities of students, have active and passive forms, are based on power relations, and the desire to assume the main roles in the group. At the same time, the following features can be distinguished: leadership style, methods and forms of interaction with the group, source of self-realization. Therefore, leaders and individuals who are prone to domination are also different in personality traits. Leaders have adequate self-esteem, low anxiety, a small communicative distance, low level of desire for power, well-developed communicative and organizational skills. Individuals who are prone to leadership domination have an overestimating self-esteem, high anxiety, a great communicative distance, a high level of desire for power, and lack of communication skills.

Conclusion. In the conditions of the development of the information society, communication and constructive influence on the person acquire special significance. This necessitates the consideration and development of leadership qualities already in the process of vocational training, when educational and educational activities lead to the emergence of a competitive specialist capable of substantiating and adopting non-typical decisions. In this regard, special attention is needed to the professional training of masters of the humanitarian profile, which not only provide interconnection on the interpersonal level and produce new humanitarian knowledge, but also act as socially active carriers of the leading ideas of society.

Thus, the article describes the theoretical principles of the development of constructive leadership of the future masters of the humanitarian profile in the process of professional training, which became the basis for the substantiation of the pedagogical conditions for the development of constructive leadership of the future masters of the humanitarian profile in the process of professional training.

According to the results of psychological and pedagogical research the theoretical approaches to the study of the problem of leadership are determined. It has been

established that constructive leadership and leadership domination are now becoming an important area of psychological and pedagogical research, which has an indisputable value in the development of a modern academic group, which occurs in parallel with the process of professional training.

Consequently, constructive leadership has a positive character, promotes the formation of a team of future masters in the academic group, while leadership domination has, in the majority, a reverse effect.

A constructive leader has to develop four main qualities: worrying about people, having strong beliefs, managing people and being able to encourage them to do business, creating conditions for people to work best. A person who is prone to leadership dominance is incapable of performing all the leadership functions in full.

Constructive leadership of the future masters of the humanitarian profile is defined as a special phenomenon in the academic group, which consists in justifying social influence on other members of the group by their motivation, conscious and constructive orientation of their educational, scientific and other activities to achieve common goals for the members of the group.

Leadership domination of future masters of the humanitarian profile is defined as a special phenomenon in the academic group, which consists in unjustified use of power to meet their own needs and the negative, often destructive, impact on the development of the academic group and the effectiveness of the educational process and is seen as a means of achieving their own mercenary goals, one from ways of expanding personal freedom and self-actualization at the expense of others.

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